

EFEKTIVITAS MODEL PEMBELAJARAN *PROBLEM SOLVING* PADA MATA PELAJARAN PEMELIHARAAN KELISTRIKAN KENDARAAN RINGAN

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan mengukur efektivitas pembelajaran dengan menerapkan model pembelajaran *problem solving*. Populasi penelitian yaitu siswa kelas XI TKR 2 SMKN 3 Bungo Kabupaten Bungo Provinsi Jambi yang berjumlah 24 siswa. Pengambilan sampel penelitian menggunakan teknik *total sampling* sehingga keseluruhan populasi merupakan sampel penelitian. Penelitian termasuk penelitian *preexperimental* menggunakan desain *one group pretest-posttest*. Instrumen penelitian menggunakan soal tes objektif pilihan ganda sejumlah 30 butir soal. Data yang terkumpul dilakukan analisis ketuntasan belajar siswa, *effect size*, dan *gain* ternormalisasi. Hasil analisis ketuntasan klasikal hasil belajar siswa menunjukkan telah tercapai ketuntasan dalam hasil belajar. Analisis *effect size* menunjukkan model pembelajaran *problem solving* memiliki efek dengan kategori besar. Hasil analisis uji *gain* ternormalisasi terjadi peningkatan kemampuan siswa dalam menerapkan model pembelajaran *problem solving* pada kategori sedang. Berdasarkan hasil penelitian, disimpulkan bahwa penerapan model pembelajaran *problem solving* terbukti efektif meningkatkan hasil belajar siswa.

Kata Kunci: efektivitas pembelajaran; *problem solving*; hasil belajar.

Abstract

The research aimed to measure the effectiveness of learning by applying the problem solving learning model. The research population was students of class XI TKR 2 SMKN 3 Bungo, Bungo Regency, Jambi Province, with a total of 24 students. Sampling using the total sampling technique so that the research sample was the entire population. This research included preexperimental research using a one-group pretest-posttest design. The research instrument used multiple choice objective test questions with a total of 30 questions. The data collected was analyzed for student learning completeness, effect size, and normalized gain. The results of the classical completeness analysis of learning outcomes showed that completeness has been achieved in learning outcomes. The effect size analysis showed that the problem solving learning model has a large category effect. The results of the normalized gain test analysis showed an increase in student's ability to apply the problem solving learning model in the medium category. It was concluded that the application of the problem solving learning model proved to be effective in increasing learning outcomes.

Keywords: learning effectiveness; *problem solving*; learning outcomes.